

The Importance of Politeness and Linguistics Aspects in Translation to Avoid Rejection

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the importance of translators' language politeness and linguistics aspects as a way to avoid rejection. The study method used was a descriptive qualitative study with a library research design. It is done at Universitas Kristen Indonesia from September 2021 to January 2022. The type of data used in this study is qualitative data, which describes some opinions, concepts, or theories that describe or present problems related to the topic of this study. Research data is taken from sources in books, journals, and offline articles. The result of the study is that the higher the understanding and mastery of the linguistic aspects of a translator, the better the translating work will be, and the translators' language politeness also influences the high and low value of acceptability. For the translation to be well received, the translators must present the translation using good vocabulary and a sentence structure that is not rigid and polite in its delivery. The translators' language politeness also makes the translation more effective and has high communication values.

Keywords: Translation, language politeness, language aspects, rejection, source language, target language

1. Introduction

Translating activities are complex activities because translating is an activity that involves two languages and two cultures, namely the culture of the source language (SL) and the target language (TL). In translating activities, translators are constantly faced with problems and challenges in treating cultural aspects implied in the source language and choosing the proper technique, method, or strategy to convey these cultural aspects in the target language. Good translating results from an excellent translation process, so those engaged in translating can say that translating should not be done haphazardly but must refer to the principles of translating. Translating transfers messages from one language into another and mostly takes place in spoken Language (Tedlock, 2011). It is in line with the opinion that translating is the process of replacing meaning from SL with TL without changing the spoken language's content (Riccardi, 2005). This understanding of the content level does not only concern the primary meaning (material meaning), ideas, or conceptions contained in the content level, but also all the information contained in the TL, namely all language norms, such as lexical meaning and grammatical meaning, and stylistic nuances expressive. In other words, translating is a study of the lexicon, grammatical structure, communication situation, and cultural contact between two languages which is carried out through analysis to determine what to mean (Naibaho, 2020).

Translating is a communication tool between the original author and the target listeners in interlingual communication. Such communication tools are needed because there is a communication gap resulting from differences in linguistic and cultural systems between the original writer and the listeners. Generally, translating activities are intended to help people who cannot understand the message directly from the source language. The essence of translating conveys the message (ideas, thoughts, feelings) from SL into TL. Supposedly, the SL mandate is translated in its entirety, both in form and meaning to the listeners (Moody, 2011).

The translation aims to produce a translating work that can present the closest meaning in the source language. Translating means reproducing in the receptor language in the closest natural equivalence of the source language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style (Yinhua, 2011). So, the translating activity focuses on efforts to produce the closest natural equivalent of the message contained in the SL into the TL. In this case, the aspect of meaning must be the main priority, and then the aspect of language style. Translating is not just a language issue but also a cultural issue. There is language and cultural transfer in translating. Therefore, the translators must examine the SL's lexicon, grammar, and cultural context before conveying the message. This message is translated into TL using the appropriate lexicon and grammar according to the TL cultural context. SL and TL certainly have different cultural colors. Therefore, the translation should be framed in the nuances of the TL culture and situation. Otherwise, the translation is inappropriate and unacceptable (Lee, 2007).

In addition, the concept between SL and TL is also a problem to interpret. There are concepts related to habits of life. For example, those used to live in snowy areas have a term to give the name snow. From falling snow to small snow drifts to snow covering leaves. While in other languages, they only know the general concept of snow. Alternatively, vice versa, in Indonesian culture, there are many terms for rice, while in other cultures, only know the term rice with the word "rice."

When the translators interpret the utterance from the source language into the target language, the translators must pay attention to aspects of communication. Translating also has a meaning that resembles the basic principle of communicating, namely conveying messages correctly (Forceville, 2014; Bonvillain, 2019). Translators must be able to convey meaning or messages from one language to another. Translating is an act of language, and each act implies a language ethic. Each of these language expressions has a different message. Therefore, in conveying the message or information, the translators will be faced with processing the meaning of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences. In other words, understanding the meaning or message is very important in translating. Translating is a form of language use, and translating is also a process that uses one language based on knowledge of another. People can transfer messages from one language to another when they understand two or more languages. In other words, the translating process reproduces meaning or messages from one language into another.

Linguistic aspects in translating activities become an inseparable part. Knowledge and ability to understand the linguistic field can be a means of translating to the maximum extent possible so that the accuracy of message delivery and grammatical adjustments between ST and ST can be carried out correctly (Bowyer-Crane et al., 2008). However, many linguists are not interested in translating; on the contrary,

many translating experts think that linguistics has no contribution to the science of translating. It can be caused by the view that translating is not a branch of science, but translating is considered an art that does not require a theoretical framework. The study of translating is not just an art related to translating a text, but translating is a scientific discipline that requires empirical research. Translating is not just an activity that only transfers SL into TL. Furthermore, translating is not only a medium but is often the object of cross-cultural written representation.

Furthermore, linguistics and other branches of linguistics, be it psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, or other branches, can be "mixed" with translating. Therefore, translating and linguistics are fields that cannot be separated. Linguistics contributes to studying and even researching the area of translating while translating is in direct contact with linguistics at the theoretical and practical levels (Naibaho, 2021; Munte & Naibaho, 2019). The relationship between the two fields illustrates that translating and linguistics can be studied separately or simultaneously. Translating theory is an approach traced from comparative linguistics (comparative linguistics), especially its semantic aspect. The transfer of messages from SL to TL in translating becomes a part that is always related to semantic problems, and other linguistic elements also have an important influence on achieving a degree of equivalence. Some linguistic elements that are important to consider in translating, among others, are problems of morphology, syntax, and semantics. Each element contributes to the translating to determine adequate equivalence.

The content of the message or idea is a central aspect of translating. To interpret well, people or translators need to refer to meaning as a central issue in the source language (SL) to be transferred into Target Language (TL). Other scientists say that translating means (1) studying the lexicon, grammatical structure, communication situation, and cultural context of the SL, (2) analyzing the SL to find its meaning, and (3) re-expressing the same meaning by using appropriate lexicon and grammatical structure in TL and its cultural context. Translating leads from the source language to a target language which is as close to an equivalent as possible and presupposes a content and style of original understanding. The translators deal with the utterance in SL as raw material that must be understood and analyzed to 'take the meaning' of SL, then 'transfer the meaning' from SL to TL, and then restructure this utterance with the same material in SL.

Therefore, the fairness of a translated utterance can be presented if the translators master the source language well and master the target language better. An excellent cultural understanding should support mastery of linguistic aspects such as morphology, syntax, and lexicon. In addition, mastery of translating materials and techniques is also an essential requirement in translating.

2. Method

The study method used was a descriptive qualitative study with a library research design. A library study can be defined as obtaining information from previous research that must be done, regardless of whether a study uses primary data or secondary data, whether the study uses field research, a laboratory, or a museum. The type of data used in this study is qualitative data, which describes some opinions, concepts, or theories that describe or present problems related to the topic of this study. Research data is taken from sources in books, journals, and offline articles. Data in this study was collected through a literature study, namely by recording, reading, studying, reviewing, or analyzing materials related to the discussed topics "translators' language politeness and linguistics aspects to avoid rejection." Analysis of research data was done through content analysis. The steps of analysis of research data are as follows: a) Research data is clarified following the problems in the research; b) Clarification results and further systematized, and c) The data that has been systematized is then analyzed to be used as a basis in concluding.

3. Discussion

Translating activities cannot be separated from the influence of linguistic aspects. Mastery of linguistic aspects can affect the translating work produced by a translator. The higher the understanding and mastery of the linguistic aspects of a translator, the better the translating work produced. The linguistic aspects contained in the language, both the source language and the target language, play a significant role in shaping the translating work (Dörnyei & Chan, 2013; Toury, 2021; Baker, 2019). Linguistic aspects have a strategic role in translating. He gives one example of grammar (grammar). Grammar determines that translators can perform translating activities well (Gile & Chai, 2009; Campbell, 2014). Without an adequate understanding of grammar or grammar, translators will have difficulty understanding the utterance and transferring meaning into TL. Therefore, grammatical adjustment is a practical theory. Grammatical adjustment is only one example of linguistic aspects when discussing linguistic aspects. Many other aspects of linguistics can help translators do their job. These aspects are phonology (including studying language sounds and their meanings), morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, sociolinguistics, and psycholinguistics (van Lier, 2004; Aronoff & Rees-Miller, 2020; Crystal, 2011). These linguistic aspects can provide a solid foundation for a linguist to become a good translator. Likewise, the existing linguistic aspects will provide a critical foundation for translating activities with students learning to interpret. From the opinions above, it can be concluded that linguistic aspects need to be understood by prospective translators. The linguistic aspect can provide a strong foundation for translators or prospective translators to carry out their activities.

Meaning can be caused by the straightforward form of the language itself, and meaning can be due to the form of the language structure used. Meaning can be caused by using the language itself, and meaning can have meant due to use in specific fields of science. Meaning can also emerge from the existing socio-cultural culture. So, it can be seen that the problem of meaning can be found in various contexts.

Concerning the translation, meaning can be grouped into five types; namely lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, contextual meaning, utterance meaning, and situational meaning. Lexical and grammatical meanings refer to the micro-linguistic context, while contextual, utterance and situational meanings refer to the micro-and macro-linguistic context. The problem of meaning in translation can be classified into five: lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, contextual or situational meaning, textual meaning, and socio-cultural meaning (Berman, 2014; Jordan, 2021).

Lexical meaning is the meaning of language elements as symbols or events. The lexical meaning can be dictionary meaning, considering the words in the dictionary regardless of their use or context (Acquaviva, Lenci, Paradis & Raffaelli, 2020). The lexical meaning is separated from the context, and the grammatical meaning is the opposite. Grammatical meaning is the relationship between language elements in larger units. Contextual or situational meaning is the meaning of a word associated with the situation of language use. Contextual meaning is the relationship between speech and the situation in which the utterance is used contextually (Sidabutar, 2020). Utterance meaning is related to the content of an utterance or discourse. Different types of contexts can also cause the meaning of a word to be different. In biology, the 'morphology' term differs from 'morphology' in the linguistic term. Socio-cultural meaning is a word closely related to language users' socio-cultural. In studying the meaning of words, it is usually distinguished between denotative and connotative meanings (Puntoni, Schroeder & Ritson, 2010). Denotative meaning is general, objective, and has not been carried with certain contents, values, or tastes.

On the other hand, the connotation is subjective because there is another meaning behind the general meaning or dictionary meaning. Use primary and secondary meanings (Jaszczolt, 2009): the primary meaning is the meaning that appears in the speaker of the language's mind when the word is spoken alone; the secondary meaning depends on the context (Dörre & Trotzke, 2019). It can be concluded that the problem of meaning in translation can be classified into six: lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, contextual or situational meaning, utterance meaning, socio-cultural meaning, and idiomatic meaning.

Lexical meaning tends to refer to the meaning in the dictionary, namely the independent meaning. For example, the word sentence means 'sentence or punishment.' It cannot be distinguished because the word is still independent. The word has not been affected by other factors. Grammatical meaning is the meaning of a word because of the influence of the sentence structure used—contextual meaning. Contextual meaning is called situational meaning (Räsänen & Rasilo, 2015; Minakova & Gural, 2015). Contextual meaning is the meaning of a word or sentence because of the situation in the use of language. Utterance meaning is the meaning that arises or is obtained from the contents of a particular spoken language. In reading about language, the word refers to using sentences and their surroundings. However, if the word is found in legal literature, the meaning will lead to punishment and something similar to it. Socio-cultural meaning is closely related to cultural culture and social relations in society. A linguist provides many good examples of family relationships, perspectives on the world of life, stereotypical terms, cultural events, language terms and greeting problems (Peeters, 2017; DeCapua & Wintergerst, 2016). The translation consumers will have difficulty understanding the terms related to these cultural issues without being explained clearly. Idiomatic meanings or other expressions—proverbs, maxims, and collocations—must be considered in the translating process. What is meant by idiomatic meaning is the meaning associated with particular expressions that already have special meanings. The idiom forms cannot be changed in composition or removed one of the word elements, added or replaced with the word element, or changed its structure. An idiom is a frozen form of language, and it is impossible to add variety to its form, and its meaning cannot be deduced from its separate components.

In translating, the accuracy of meaning becomes fundamental, better known as the term equivalence of meaning (Gough, 2019; Su, 2019). Furthermore, to equalize understanding, the accuracy of meaning is changed to the equivalence of meaning. This equivalence of meaning is the core of a translating activity. It is because translating transfers the equivalent meaning from one language to another. So, the equivalence of meaning becomes a significant necessity in translating activities.

Meanwhile, the equivalence of meaning in translating will determine the success or failure because, in principle, translating is the message of an equivalent transfer from one language to another. Descriptively, equivalence refers to the apparent relationship between utterances in SL and TL which correspond to one another directly. Prescriptively equivalence refers to SL expression and its standard translation in TL, for example, in a dictionary (Shuttleworth, 2014; Fernández, 2013). Equivalence is also one of the procedures in translating. Equivalence in translating refers to the harmony of meaning between SL and TL expressions. Meanwhile, the total equivalence of meaning in translating is impossible because the utterance is bound by a particular language and culture (House, 2006).

The total equivalence in translating is impossible. Meanwhile, Rochayah Machali explained that equivalence is no similarity (Pramono, 2014). In translating, the equivalence of meaning should not be seen as total equivalence but only partial equivalence because all aspects of the terms in SL are not always included when translated into TL (Dewar, 2017). In translating, the shift occurs not only at the form level and the message level. Concerning this shift in form and message, the shift can be tolerated so that equivalence is maintained as he states that translators should maintain referential meaning above all interference from other parties in translating activities (Diriker, 2004). So, the equivalence is still acceptable as long as the existing changes do not cause truth changes. Equivalence is divided based on language, namely a formal structure and a communication system. Based on the nature of this language, equivalence in translating is divided into two: formal equivalence, context-free equivalence, and functional equivalence, equivalence oriented to the values of communication (Khan, Abid & Abid, 2020). In addition, equivalence is divided into two, formal and dynamic equivalence. Formal equivalence focuses on messages that include both form and content. This equivalence is intended so that the translator understands the listeners as much as possible in the SL context. Dynamic equivalence is based on the principle of commensurate effects. Listeners of translated utterances will feel the same way as speakers of SL.

Meanwhile, three possible equivalences in translating are equivalence at the form level, reference equivalence, and equivalence at the functional level (Burgos, Lai, Pei, Wang, Boroyevich & Pou, 2008; Pym, 2009). Due to these three levels of equivalence, equivalence in translating can be achieved with only one level of equivalence. Thus, equivalence becomes the main thing for translating activities. The equivalence of meaning becomes the focus of every activity the translators carry out. From the description above, it can be concluded that the equivalence of meaning in translating activities is fundamental. Translators must be careful when looking for equivalent words, phrases, clauses, or sentences in translating utterances from SL into TL. Errors in the selection of equivalents will certainly significantly affect the translation results. Thus, errors in translating are usually determined by errors when choosing the equivalence of meaning between SL and TL.

Acceptability is one of the factors in assessing the translating work. Acceptance is used to see the translating results related to the level of fairness. For the translation to be received well, the translators must present the translation using good vocabulary and a sentence structure that is not rigid. Acceptability refers to whether translating has been expressed following the applicable rules, norms, and culture in the target language or not, both at the micro and macro levels (Touy, 2021; Vandepitte, 2017). The acceptability concept is fundamental because even though a translation is accurate in terms of content or message, the translation will be rejected by the target listeners if the method of expression is contrary to the rules, norms, and culture of the target language. "In translating, the translators try to convey the meaning of the source language to the target language listeners by using appropriate grammatical forms and vocabulary" (Musyoka & Karanja, 2014; Mellinger, 2017; González-Davies & Enríquez-Raído, 2016). Acceptability in translating consists of two parts. The first part deals with sentence structure, while the second part deals with lexical. The translators must adjust the sentence structure because every language has a different sentence structure. Thus, the translators are bound to the meaning and use of sentence structures to be well received or have a high fairness value.

Acceptability is related to a person's preference for word choice, sentence, or paragraph construction (Quirk & Svartvik, 2019). TL speakers may generally accept two synonymous words, but assessors can be provoked to improve because they are based on taste. The appraiser should not impose his taste. Furthermore, one of the indicators that the translating is reasonable is if the meaning communicated into the TL uses normal/natural grammatical and vocabulary forms. Thus, from the various opinions above, it can be concluded that acceptability is also very important in translating accuracy and legibility. The acceptability of the translating can be seen from the use of good vocabulary and a non-rigid sentence structure. Listeners feel comfortable accepting the translated utterance fairly and do not feel "foreign" when reading it.

An utterance can be translated because it is well-spoken, meaning that it has a pleasant style of language, a good rhythm, and moves at an acceptable pace. Remember that what can be read by one audience may not be read by another. Here, interpretability is essential. The higher the interpretability of the translated utterance, the easier it is for the listeners to understand the content of the reading. Interpretability is the degree of ease of writing to understand its meaning (Scholz & Dorner, 2013). Interpretability is how easily an utterance is intended to be understood (Grzech, 2020). Based on this understanding, it can be understood that the interpretability of an utterance involves language problems and the content of the language.

The factors that affect the level of utterance interpretability include the use of new words, the use of foreign and regional words, the use of taxa words and taxa sentences, the use of foreign sentences, the use of incomplete sentences, the average length of sentences, and the use of complex sentences (Sun et al., 2020). The use of new words in an utterance, on the one hand, can enrich the vocabulary of an utterance. However, on the other hand, using these new words can result in low utterance interpretability. The more an utterance uses new words that are still foreign to the listener, the lower the interpretability of the utterance will be. Likewise, the use of foreign and regional words, the more an utterance uses foreign and regional words, the more difficult it will be for listeners to understand the contents of the utterance. The word taxa and sentence taxa are words and sentences with multiple meanings. Using such words and sentences in an utterance will make it

difficult for the listeners to understand the contents, primarily if no context guides them to determine the meaning of these taxa words and sentences. However, with adequate context, the ambiguity in the sentence can be overcome. Incomplete sentences can also cause difficulty in understanding the contents of the sentence.

An incomplete sentence cannot be measured by the sentence length but by fulfilling the functions that should exist in the sentence. For example, the sentence: "People sitting on the edge of an apparent pool that seems to not pay attention to what is happening around him." Although this sentence is quite long, there is one function that should exist but is not fulfilled, namely, the predicate function. The sentence only fulfills one of the functions of the sentence, namely the subject, so the sentence's content is challenging to understand. The average sentence length is also one of the factors that determine interpretability. Long sentences require higher concentration than short sentences. Reading a sentence should not stop before the sentence is finished reading because the sentence contains a complete idea. If we stop reading a sentence in the middle of a sentence, we will be disturbed or not fluent in understanding its meaning. In this regard, long sentences will make it difficult for the listeners to understand the content because when reading long sentences, they may stop reading before the sentence is finished.

Likewise, complex sentences, this type of sentence also affects the level of interpretability. Complex sentences are generally long sentences because complex sentences are a combination of two or more single sentences. The more single sentences combined into a complex sentence, the longer the sentence will be and the more difficult it will be to understand its contents. From the description above, it can be concluded that the writing style of the translators largely determines legibility. The choice of words and the determination of the type of sentence will significantly affect a manuscript's interpretability level. The legibility of each manuscript is undoubtedly different and depends a lot on the script maker or translators who carry out the activity.

Language politeness is essential in the acceptability aspect. Acceptability can be understood as using vocabulary and sentence structures that are reasonable or inappropriate in the target language (Canale, 2014; Simatupang & Naibaho, 2021; Brown, 2015). In other words, acceptability is also closely related to the translators' ability to process the translation results by using language politeness at the lexical level of vocabulary choices and applying sentence structure so that it is appropriately accepted and meets the rules of the target language. Therefore, the translators must be observant in determining vocabulary and deciphering the translating results in the target language based on language politeness.

Language politeness will impact the translating results because the translators play language politeness. The delivery of a good and polite message will undoubtedly increase the listeners' interest in completing the reading thoroughly. The politeness of the language the translators use also makes the translation more effective and has high communication values (Drugan, 2017; Lefebure, 2019; Orlando, 2019). Communicative translating results certainly has a strategic role. Good communication values need to be used by translators in transferring the translating results. It is known that the translator is also a mediator between the writer and the listeners. Mediator here means that the translators become the liaison of the writer in conveying the meaning or message to the listeners. Thus, the translators must convey the message properly, correctly, and politely. One of the criteria is the result of communicative translating to obtain these results. When the translator uses the values of good communication, he must pay attention to the politeness aspect of language. It is because politeness in language can deliver translating results with communicative value.

The politeness of language also directs the right listeners. Translators always pay attention to aspects of the target listeners. By knowing the target listeners, translators can consider the use of language according to the target listeners of the translated results. Of course, politeness in the language is one of the considerations for translators. By paying attention to the aspect of the target listeners, the translators can process the results of the translation properly wrapped in polite language so that the translating results will feel good.

Thus, politeness in language can reflect the aspect of acceptance. The translating results can have a high acceptability value if the translating or translating effect results are high. It is because politeness in language gives a different color to the presentation of the translating results. The listeners will be more and more immersed in it. It feels natural, and the technical terms are familiar to the listeners. The phrases and sentences used also follow the rules in the target language. The results of the translating are expressed well and politely. Thus, politeness in language can give different colors to the translating results. Therefore, politeness in language can lead listeners to enjoy translating better. So, politeness in the language is a reflection for translators in considering aspects of acceptability.

4. Conclusion

Based on this description, it can be concluded that translating is a complex activity, so translators must pay attention to aspects of communication. Translators deal with the meaning of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences in conveying the message. So, understanding the meaning or message is very important in translating. The higher the understanding and mastery of the linguistic aspects of a translator, the better the translating work will be. There are six meanings in translating: lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, contextual or situational meaning, utterance meaning, socio-cultural meaning, and idiomatic meaning. Acceptability is one of the factors in assessing the translating work. Acceptance is used to see the translating results related to the level of fairness. For the translation to be well received, the translators must present the translation using good vocabulary and a sentence structure that is not rigid and polite in its delivery. This politeness of language becomes essential in the aspect of acceptance. Translators must be observant in determining vocabulary and deciphering the translating results in the target language based on language politeness. Language politeness will have a higher translating effect. The politeness of the translators' language also makes the translation more effective and has high communication values. It is because politeness in language can deliver translating results with communicative value. Translators must process the translating results politely and adequately so that the translating results will feel good. The high and low acceptability value is also influenced by the politeness of the translators' language in describing the translation results.

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Bio-note:

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